

EFFECT OF PLANT-BASED STABILIZERS ON THE QUALITY OF ICE LOLLIES

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ABSTRACT

This study is aimed to assess the effect of stabilizers viz., guar gum and carrageenan on the quality parameters of ice lollies. Ice lollies a niche product category in the existing frozen food market. The effect of stabilizers was studied on the various physicochemical properties such as freezing time, melting rate, Brix, pH, acidity and sensory properties. From the study it was found that there was no change in pH for all the three samples, there was a slight change in Brix and acidity, the freezing time of control and T1 did not have any difference whereas T2 took a lot more time than other samples, the total melting time of T1 showed highly acceptable results as it took 65 minutes for time final meltdown, whereas both control and T2 comparatively melted very quickly. Hence from the physicochemical parameters and sensory analysis T1 – combination of guar gum and carrageenan showed remarkable results.

Keywords–Ice lollies, Frozen desserts, stabilizers, freezing time, flavours.

INTRODUCTION

The essential ingredients of commercially produced ice lollies are water and sugar, followed by flavours, colours, an acidity regulator, and a stabiliser. Ice lollies, commonly referred to as ice pops or popsicles, are fruit-flavoured, water-based frozen snack foods that are sold on sticks or in cube form. The market for Frozen products is divided into sections based on flavour, category, product type, and distribution method. During COVID-19, the frozen food industry suffered as a result of supply chain interruptions, especially because of logistical constraints on transportation and shipping, which had an impact on ice-lollies sales.

Additionally, market sales were affected by the lack of the massive labour force needed in production units and the interruption of in-store sales at speciality shops, supermarkets, and

convenience stores as a result of subsequent lockdowns and store closures. Despite suffering greatly as a result of the pandemic, numerous businesses predicted that by the end of 2020, the take-home consumption segment will significantly grow in the industry, hence products such as ready-to-freeze ice lollies, candy and pop's came into the market but the major problem they faced was the products not getting frozen at the particular given time or not getting frozen at all, hence this study aimed to bridge the research gap and bring out the action of stabilizers in ice lollies in the quality, texture and overall acceptability of the product As a natural emulsifier and stabiliser, guar gum powder is used. Main purpose of using guar gum in frozen products is stabilization. Guar gum has important role in ice cream stabilization (Mudgil. et al., 2014) because of its water binding properties. One of the many advantages it offers to frozen desserts and other manufacturing businesses is that it aids in the creation of the smooth and velvety structure of dessert items. Shrinkage, one of the main issues with frozen food storage, is also resolved by guar gum, from The preliminary trial it was also found that it Provides resistance to melting, Retards and reduces large ice crystal formation and improves the texture and mouthfeel of the frozen product. The FDA typically recognises food-grade carrageenan, an ingredient derived from a species of red seaweed called Irish moss, as being safe. carrageenan is particularly suitable for firm, creamy textures in dairy desserts. (Blakemore, et al., 2010) It thickens, binds, and stabilises certain (usually high-fat) meals, such as ice cream, preventing the separation of the constituents. It's one of the numerous industrial stabilisers and gelling chemicals that can be used in ice cream and other frozen goods to save

	Control	T1	T2
Ingredients	% Used per 100 gm (%)	% Used per 100 gm (%)	% Used per 100 gm
RO water	80.31	80.29	80.3
Natural sugar 1	11.2	11.2	11.2
Natural sugar 2	7.8	7.8	7.8
Natural Sweetener	0.02	0.02	0.02
Guar gum powder	0	0.01	0.01
Carrageenan	0	0.01	0
Natural colour	0.07	0.07	0.07
Natural flavour	0.190	0.190	0.190
Acidity regulator	0.4	0.4	0.4
Natural preservative	0.01	0.01	0.01

Flow chart for preparation of ice lollies

MATERIALS AND METHODS

RO water, natural sugars, acidity regulator, preservative, stabilizers – guar gum & carrageenan, natural flavour, natural colour, natural sweetener, all of them procured from the local market in Hyderabad.

Figure 1: Process flowchart of ice lollies preparation

As given in the Fig 1, RO water is heated up to 60°C, in a magnetic stirrer, followed by which Natural sugars & sweeteners are added, stabilizers are added then the overall mixture is heated up to 70-75°C, and the mixture is allowed to pasteurize for 30 minutes. Homogenization is done for 2-3 minutes post pasteurization. Colour, flavour, acidity regulator and preservative are added and the mixture is allowed to blend for 20 minutes in a magnetic stirrer, once done, lost and evaporated water is made up of its initial volume with RO water.

The product is allowed to cool, and 50 gm of samples is aseptically packaged in a polyethylene tube and stored at room temperature until further analysis. The samples are analysed for the freezing time, total melting time Physico chemical (pH, acidity and brix) and sensory analysis.

PHYSICO CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Total soluble solids (Brix)

The TSS of Ice lollies were analyzed by hand refractometer (TAMCO, Model No. 90021) using the method as depicted in the AOAC (2006). Homogenous samples were collected on a calibrated refractometer's prism and direct reading (Brix) was taken on scales

Ph

The pH content was determined by (M. Tronic digital-255) pH meter.

Titration Acidity

Titration acidity is determined by titration against 0.1N NaOH soluble using a few drops of phenolphthalein indicator.

Total Melting time

The meltdown rate was determined according to Al-saleh, et al., (2011) by carefully cutting the zip lock bags and placing the frozen samples (pre-weighed as 50 g), onto a glass funnel and measuring the amount of water that drained into the measuring cylinder at $20 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Total melting time was expressed as the total time taken for the 50 gm of sample to completely melt at room temperature.

Freezing time

Time taken to freeze in the intervals of 4 hr, 6 hr, 8 hr and 16 hr were examined and the data collected is tabulated

Sensory evaluation

panellists were selected to judge the sensory properties of the ice lollies, Ice lollies samples were evaluated for texture, flavour, taste, and colour using five-point hedonic scales, with the highest number indicating an extreme liking and the lowest indicating an extreme dislike. Panellists were also asked to note texture changes and melting characteristics, All ice lollies (in 50g cups) were coded with A,B and C Randomly and presented to panellists on a tray in individual booths.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical parameter

Figure 2: sensory graph

Table 2: physical analysis of Ice lollies

Sample	Freezing time - hours	Total Melting time - minutes
Control	4 hr	50 min
T1	4 hr	65 min
T2	12 hr	55 min

From the above results, it was observed that both control and formulation 1 got frozen in 4 hours whereas formulation 2 took 12 hours to get frozen and it was also observed that out of 3 trials, all 3 had variation in time of freezing, hence T1 shows better quality in freezing time and melting rate than control and T2 because of the combination of guar gum and carrageenan (Salehi, 2020).

CHEMICAL PARAMETERS

Table 3: chemical analysis of ice lollies

sample	pH	acidity	brix
control	2.85	0.64%	16.4
T1	2.85	0.45%	16.9
T2	2.85	0.57%	16

From the above results, there is no variant in pH, there is a slight variation in acidity and Brix among all three samples.

SENSORY PARAMETERS

Figure 2: sensory graph

From the above graph, it was observed That formulation 1 (combination of guar gum and carrageenan) was preferred over the other samples because control had a poor texture and also melted very quickly, it gave a very watery taste rather than fruity, T2 had a very soft texture which was not ideal for Ice lollies and kept breaking and did not hold its shape, whereas T1 provided an overall good texture with better mouthfeel and taste.

Figure 3: Different samples of ice lollies

CONCLUSION

Two samples were developed using carrageenan and guar gum at varying proportions and control without any stabilizers. The future success of lollies in market place depends on the ability of the product to freeze at a particular time, thereby providing better taste and quality to the product. From the trials, it was observed that the combination of carrageenan and guar gum works well and gives better sensory and physicochemical properties than the other two samples. There is a huge difference in the melting rate of T1 compared to control and T2, there is not much of a difference in freezing time for control and T1, and the chemical parameters such as acidity, Brix and pH have a very slight difference. The outcomes of this study also indicated that the ice lollies' sensory parameters of T1 were highly acceptable and can be a great success in the market.

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